

stems of the respective resistant and susceptible varieties were collected from 80-day-old healthy plants. Fresh plant samples were lyophilized for 6 hours, and 300 mg of lyophilized samples were extracted in 80% ethanol by grinding with mortar and pestle, and then filtered. Total free amino acids, phenol, and soluble sugars were chemically analyzed as per standard procedures using the ethanol extract of the material. The data for gall midge and stem borer resistance are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Results indicated that varieties PTB 18, PTB 21, and Leuang 152, which are highly resistant to gall midge, had relatively higher content of free amino acids and phenols and less sugars in their shoot apices than the susceptible varieties Jaya and IR8. In the case of the stem borer, on the other hand, the stems of both TKM6 (resistant) and Ratna (moderately resistant), a derivative of

Table 1. Biochemical constituents of vegetative shoot apices of selected rice varieties resistant and susceptible to gall midge. CRRI, Cuttack, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a to gall midge	Biochemical constituents (mg/g dry tissue)		
		Free amino acids	Phenols	Soluble sugars
PTB 18	R	24.8	5.5	12.0
PTB 21	R	32.5	7.8	10.8
Leuang 152	R	15.4	4.6	10.7
Jaya	S	9.3	4.4	19.0
IR8	S	9.7	3.8	19.7

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible.

Table 2. Biochemical constituents of stems of selected rice varieties resistant and susceptible to yellow stem borer. CRRI, Cuttack, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a to yellow stem borer	Biochemical constituents (mg/g dry tissue)		
		Free amino acids	Phenols	Soluble sugars
TKM6	R	2.0	2.5	21.2
Ratna	MR	3.9	1.8	30.5
IR8	S	13.7	4.4	50.3

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

the cross TKM6/IR8, have less amino acids, phenols, and sugars than the susceptible IR8. However, it was not determined whether the relative levels of

free amino acids, phenols, and soluble sugars were related to the resistance of these varieties to gall midge and stem borers. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Rice varietal reactions to iron toxicity on acid sulfate soil

F. N. Ponnampertuma, principal soil chemist; and J. L. Solivas, research assistant, International Rice Research Institute

In 3 seasons, 420 rices were screened for iron toxicity tolerance in an acid sulfate soil in a farmer's field in Albay Province, Philippines. The soil was a Sulfaquept (pH 3.5, organic carbon 1.2% active iron 2.5%, active manganese 0.001%, exchangeable sulfate 0.27%, and available phosphorus 7 mg/kg).

The field was puddled and harrowed after broadcasting 50 kg N/ha and 25 kg P/ha. Three-week-old seedlings, raised in a normal seedbed, were planted in three 3-m rows at a 20 × 20 cm spacing in randomized complete blocks replicated 3 times. A resistant check and a susceptible check were among the rices tested. The field was irrigated from a nearby stream. The plants were scored 4 weeks after transplanting for iron toxicity on foliar symptoms and general appearance,

using the scale 1 to 9 (1 = almost normal plant, and 9 = almost dead or dead plant). A score of 3 or lower indicated tolerance.

Table 1 summarizes the results. Forty-one rices showed tolerance for iron toxicity. Outstanding among them were IR36, IR3839-1, IR4442-165-1-3-2,

Table 1. Distribution of iron toxicity scores in field mass screening of rices during 3 seasons on an acid sulfate soil, Malinao, Albay, Philippines.

Varieties tested	Season	Rices (no.)	Score ^a distribution								
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
IRON 1978	1979 dry	262	0	0	36	166	57	2	1	0	0
1979 GEU Elite	1979 wet	85	0	0	0	5	15	33	23	9	0
1980 GEU Elite	1980 dry	73	0	0	5	39	26	3	0	0	0
Total		420	0	0	41	210	98	38	24	0	0

^aOn the scale 1 to 9 (1 = almost normal plant, 9 = almost dead or dead plant).

Table 2. Iron toxicity scores and grain yield of 7 selected rices in 3 seasons on an acid sulfate soil, Albay, Philippines.^a

Variety or line	1979 dry		1979 wet		1980 dry			
	Score	Yield (t/ha)	Score	Yield (t/ha)	Score	Yield (t/ha)		
IR26	4.8	1.7	f	7.2	^b	Not tested		
IR36	3.3	2.5	de	Not tested	^b	3.7	5.2	cde
IR42	Not tested			6.0		5.3	5.9	abc
IR44	Not tested			5.2	2.1	4.0	6.3	abc
IR46	4.0	3.2	bc	4.5	2.6	4.0	6.4	ab
IR4422-180-2	Not tested			5.0	2.7	4.7	4.6	def
IR4683-54-2	2.5	4.5	a	5.0	2.4	3.0	6.7	a

^aIn a column, values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. The plants were scored 4 weeks after transplanting, on the 1-9 scale. ^bNot harvested.

IR4568-225-3-2, IR4625-269-4-2, IR5853-118-5, IR8192-200-3-3-1-1, IR9129-136-2, IR13419-113-1, IR13240-10-1-3-2, IR13423-17-1-2-1, IR14632-246-2, IR19743-46-2-3, B2149-PN-26-1-1, BPI R1-2, and IET 1444.

Fifteen rices were evaluated in replicated yield trials in the same field in each season. The plot size was 2 × 3 m in the first season and 3 × 4 m in the two other seasons. Cultural practices were the same as for the mass-screening.

Grain yields of seven selected rices and iron toxicity scores in three seasons are in Table 2.

In the 1979 dry season, IR4683-54-2

gave the lowest score (2.5) and the highest yield (4.5 t/ha); IR26, the susceptible check, gave the highest toxicity score (4.8) and the lowest yield (1.7 t/ha).

There were no other correlations between symptoms 4 weeks after transplanting and grain yield.

In the 1979 wet season, iron toxicity was severe because of soil acidification in the dry months preceding the wet season. The toxicity scores were high and the yields were low. But, IR4422-480-2, IR4683-54-2 and IR46, which were among the top yielders in the dry season experiment, also were among the best in the wet season. IR26, the sus-

ceptible check, and IR42 suffered severely from iron toxicity. Their maturity was so delayed that they could not be harvested with the rest.

During the 1980 dry season, iron toxicity was not severe (apparently due to the wet soil during the rainy months before planting), scores were low, and the yield was high. IR4683-54-2 was again the highest yielder. IR46 also showed tolerance for excess iron in both score and yield.

IR46 and IR4683-54-2 may be suited to acid sulfate soils in which the main growth-limiting factor is iron toxicity. ■

Decimal scoring systems for drought reaction and recovery ability in rice screening nurseries

G. C. Loresto and T. T. Chang, International Rice Research Institute

Tall traditional varieties differ from semidwarfs in their visible responses to water stress. In the past workers have often given more attention to drought resistance at the vegetative growth

stages than to responses at the reproductive phase, which is more closely related to grain yield. Recovery from drought stress also deserves attention. We have devised decimal scoring sys-

Table 1. Scoring^a system for drought resistance screening at vegetative phases I and II.^b IRRI, 1981.

Decimal score	Plant type	Stress symptoms			
		Leaf rolling	Leaf drying	Plant color	Growth stunting
1	Tall traditional types	Slight folding from early morning to late afternoon	No drying	Remains green	No stunting
	Semidwarf types	No rolling	Few leaf tips drying	Green	
3	Tall traditional types	Partial rolling from early morning to late afternoon	Few tips drying more than 1 cm in length; 5–10% basal leaves dried	Green	”
	Semidwarf types	No rolling	75% leaf-tip drying extended to 1/4 of leaf blade; 5–10% of lower leaves dried	Green	”
5	Tall traditional types	Complete and tight rolling from early morning to late afternoon. Partial unrolling when temperature cools during day; complete unrolling at night	Most younger leaf tips dried; 25–40% lower leaves dried	Unusually dark green	”
	Semidwarf types	Complete and tight rolling; partial unrolling at night	50% younger leaves with 1/2 – 1/3 area dried; 25–40% lower leaves dried	Ashen gray or yellow	Slight
7	Tall traditional types	Tube-like rolling; no unrolling at night	Most upper leaves with 2/3 – 3/4 area dried; 60–80% lower leaves dried	Ashen gray or yellow	Stunted
	Semidwarf types	Same as tall traditional			
9	Tall traditional types	Tube-like rolling; no unrolling at night	100% of all leaves dried; plants generally approach permanent wilting, some die	Meristematic tissues show a slight green to light green tinge	Severe stunting
	Semidwarf types	Same as tall traditional			

^aScores were taken 15–20 days from the start of imposed stress or when the susceptible checks showed symptoms of moisture stress. Preliminary scoring should be taken when plants show the first signs of stress. ^bVegetative phase I refers to the active tillering stage of both the early and late-maturing varieties, and ranges from 50 to 60 days after seeding (DS). Vegetative phase II applies only to the late-maturing varieties at about 80–100 DS.